

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ
JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

ДАВРИЙЛИГИ: 2016-2025

ЖИЛД 10
СОҢ 4

2025

ЧОП
ЭТИЛГАН САНА:
05.09.2025

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

10 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 10, НОМЕР 4

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 10, ISSUE 4

Бош мухаррир:

Ризаев Жасур Алимжанович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети ректори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Ўзбекистон Республикаси
Фанлар академиясининг Иммунология ва инсон
геномикаси институти директор ўринбосари,
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Масъул котиб:

Самиева Гулноза Утқуровна
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Нашр учун масъул:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
онкология кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

ТАХРИРИЯТ КЕНГАШИ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

Иммунология ва инсон геномикаси институти директори –
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Ўзбекистон
Республикаси Фанлар академияси академиги

Jin Young Choi

Сеул миллий университети Стоматология мактаби оғиз ва
юз-жағ жарроҳлиги департаменти профессори, Жанубий
Кореянинг юз-жағ ва эстетик жарроҳлик ассоциацияси
президенти

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна

тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети проректори, 1-клиникаси бош
врачи. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети Гистология, цитология ва
эмбриология кафедраси мудири
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

тиббиёт фандар доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети болалар жарроҳлиги кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент тиббиёт
академияси Оилавий тиббиётда акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси профессори **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9313-4918

Очилов Улугбек Усмонович

DSc, доцент, СамДТУ Дипломдан кейинги таълим
факултети Психиатрия курси мудири. СамДТУ Илмий
кенгаши котиби. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>

Шавази Наргиз Нуралiena

DSc. Доцент, СамДМУ 3-сон акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси мудири <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>

Юлдашев Равшан Захидович

Тоҷикистон Давлат тиббиёт университети Онкология
ва нур таъхиси кафедраси мудири, Тиббиёт фанлари
доктори, Профессор. Душанбе, Тоҷикистон.
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>

Саидов Сандамир Абборович

тиббиёт фанлар доктори,
Тошкент фармацевтика институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428

Бабалджанов Ойбек Абдуҷаббарович

тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент педиатрия
тиббиёт институти, Тери-таносил, болалар тери-таносил
касалликлари ва ОИТС кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Тошкент
педиатрия тиббиёт институти Факультет болалар
хирургия кафедраси. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-5409-4327

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

тиббиёт фанлари доктори,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
№2-сон Педиатрия, неонатология ва болалар
касалликлари пропедевтикаси кафедраси доценти.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
Тошкент давлат стоматология институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети, онкология кафедраси профессори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503

Даминов Феруз Асадуллаевич

Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
2-сон Даволаш факультети декани,
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент.
Самарқанд, Ўзбекистон.

Миржурев Элбек Миршавкатович

тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
ЎзССВ Тиббий ходимларни касбий малакасини
ривожлантириши марказининг Нейрореабилитация
кафедраси мудири, Тошкент, Ўзбекистон

Тагаев Шерқабул Бойқабдулович

тиббиёт фанлари доктори, хирургия кафедраси
доценти Тошкент давлат стоматология институти.
ORCID: 0009-0004-7661-9253.

Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналлов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Главный редактор:

Ризаев Жасур Алимджанович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ректор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0001-5468-9403

Заместитель главного редактора:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
доктор медицинских наук, Заместитель директора Института иммунологии и геномики человека Академии наук Республики Узбекистан, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-3933

Ответственный секретарь:

Самиева Гульноза Уткуровна
доктор медицинских наук, профессор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-6142-7054

Ответственный за публикацию:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, доцент кафедры онкологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-0888-9150

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

директор Института иммунологии и геномики человека доктор медицинских наук, профессор, академик АН РУз

Jin Young Choi

профессор департамента оральной и челюстно-лицевой хирургии школы стоматологии Стоматологического госпиталя Сеульского национального университета, Президент Корейского общества челюстно-лицевой и эстетической хирургии

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, проректор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, заведующий кафедрой Гистологии, цитологии и эмбриологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-0615-0144

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Детской хирургии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-2650-4445

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

Доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры акушерства и гинекологии Семейной медицины Ташкентской медицинской академии **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9313-4918

Очилов Улугбек Усманович

DSc, доцент, заведующий курсом психиатрии факультета постдипломного образования СамГМУ. Секретарь Ученого совета СамГМУ. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>

Шавази Наргиз Нуралиевна

DSc, доцент, заведующая кафедрой акушерства и гинекологии N 3 СамГМУ. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>

Юлдашев Равшан Захидович

Заведующий кафедрой Онкологии и лучевой диагностики Таджикского медицинского университета, д.м.н., профессор, Душанбе, Таджикистан <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>

Сандов Сандамир Аброрович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский фармацевтический институт **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-6616-5428

Бабаджанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский педиатрический медицинский институт, доцент кафедры Дерматовенерологии, детская дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Факультетской детской хирургии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-5409-4327

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии, неонатологии и переподготовки детских болезней №2 Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергатовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры онкологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета **ORCID ID:** 0000-0001-5272-5503

Даминов Феруз Асадуллаевич

Декан лечебного факультета №2 Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, доктор медицинских наук, доцент. Самарканд, Узбекистан.

Мирджураев Эльбек Миршавкатович

Заведующий кафедрой Нейрореабилитации Центра развития профессиональной квалификации медицинских работников МЗ РУз, д.м.н., профессор Ташкент, Узбекистан

Тагаев Шеркабул Бойкабулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры хирургии, Ташкентский государственный стоматологический институт. **ORCID:** 0009-0004-7661-9253.

Верстка: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Chief Editor:

Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich
MD, DSc, Professor of Dental Medicine,
Rector of the Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Deputy Chief Editor:

Ziyadullaev Shukhrat Khudayberdievich
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Deputy Director of the Institute
of Immunology and Human Genomics of the Academy of
Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Responsible secretary:

Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna
doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Responsible for publication:

Shakhanova Shakhnoza Shavkatovna
PhD, Docent Department of Oncology
Samarkand State medical university
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

EDITORIAL BOARD:

Aripova Tamara Uktamovna

*Director of the Institute of Immunology and Human Genomics -
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Academician of the
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

Jin Young Choi

*Professor Department of Oral and Maxillofacial
Surgery School of Dentistry Dental Hospital
Seoul National University, President of the
Korean Society of Maxillofacial Aesthetic Surgery*

Abdullaeva Nargiza Nurmatovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Vice-Rector
Samarkand State Medical University, Chief Physician of
the 1st Clinic ORCID ID: 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Oripov Firdavs Suratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Head of the Department of Histology, Cytology and
Embryology of Samarkand State Medical University.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Mavlyanov Farkhod Shavkatovich

*Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of Pediatric
Surgery, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Magzumova Nargiza Makhamovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department
of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Family Medicine, Tashkent
Medical Academy. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Ochilov Ulugbek Usmanovich

*DSc, Docent, Head of the Psychiatry Course at the Faculty of
Postgraduate Education of SamSMU. Secretary of the Academic
Council of SamSMU. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>*

Shavazi Nargiz Nuraliyena

*DSc, Associate Professor, Head of the Department of Obstetrics
and Gynecology N 3 of Samarkand State Medical University.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

Yuldashev Ravshan Zakhidovich

*Head of the Department of Oncology and Radiation Diagnostics
at Tajik State Medical University, Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor. Dushanbe, Tajikistan <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>*

Saidov Saidamir

*Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute,
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Babadjanov Oybek Abdujabbarovich

*Doctor of sciences in medicine, Tashkent Pediatric
Medical Institute, Docent the Department of
Dermatovenerology, pediatric dermatovenerology
and AIDS, ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute,
Faculty of Children Department of Surgery.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

Yuldashev Botir Akhmatovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
Pediatrics, Neonatology and Propaedeutics of Pediatrics,
Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ibragimova Malika Xudayberganovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Tashkent State Dental Institute
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxammatkulovich

*DSc, Professor of Oncology,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Daminov Feruz Asadullaevich

*Dean of the Faculty of Medicine No. 2, Samarkand State
Medical University, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate
Professor. Samarkand, Uzbekistan.*

Mirjuraev Elbek Mirshavkatovich

*Head of the Department of Neurorehabilitation Center
for the development of professional qualification of
medical workers, Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor. Tashkent, Uzbekistan
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-2111-4388>*

Tagaev Sher Kabul Baykabulovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor
of Surgery Department, Tashkent State Dental Institute
ORCID: 0009-0004-7661-9253.*

Page Maker: Khurshid Mirzakhmedov

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY

1. **Babazhanova Shakhida Dadazhanovna, Ibragimova Feruza Abdikarimovna, Abdurakhmanova Zilola Hamidullah kizi**
ORGAN-PRESERVING TACTICS IN CASE OF OVARIAN TORSION IN ADOLESCENT GIRLS.....11
2. **Jilonova Asalkhon Nigmatillo qizi, Nasirova Khurshidakhon Kudratullaevna, Shodieva Khurshida Tukhtasinovna**
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN HYPOTHYROIDISM AND THE STATE OF OVARIAN RESERVE IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE WITH INFERTILITY.....21
3. **Khamrayev Khumoyun Khamzayevich**
HYGIENE ISSUES IN PREGNANT WOMEN IN THE CONTEXT OF UROLOGICAL DISEASES.....27
4. **Rizaeva Malika Abdumanonovna, Kattakhodjaeva Makhmuda Khamdamovna, Rizaev Jasur Alimdjanovich**
MOLECULAR AND REGENERATIVE INNOVATIONS IN GYNECOLOGY: INTEGRATION PERSPECTIVES IN THE POST-COVID ERA.....31
5. **Sirojiddinova Khiromon Nuriddinovna**
PATHOGENETIC VALUES OF IMMUNE COMPLEXES DURING INTRAUTERINE INFECTION.....45
6. **Uktamova Yulduz Umarovna, Khudoyarova Dildora Rakhimovna**
IDENTIFICATION OF RISK FACTORS AND PATHOGENESIS OF PREECLAMPSIA (LITERATURE REVIEW).....51

INFECTIOUS DISEASES

7. **Axmedova Gulchehra Abdullayevna, Shukhurova Dilorom Baxodirovna**
EVALUATION OF THE CLINICAL COURSE OF MYOCARDITIS AND MYOPERICARDITIS IN PATIENTS WITH COVID-19.....59
8. **Akhmedova Gulchekhhra Abdullayevna, Shukhurova Dilorom Baxodirovna**
EVALUATION OF THE ROLE OF POLYMORPHIC GENES MMP-9 AND TIMP-1 IN MYOCARDITIS CAUSED BY SARS-COV-2.....69

PEDIATRICS DISEASES

9. **Tashmatova Gulnoza Aloyevna, Khalilova Zilola Abdurauf qizi**
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE INTESTINAL MICROBIOME IN CHILDREN WITH BRONCHIAL ASTHMA ASSOCIATED WITH MYCOPLASMA AND CHLAMYDIA INFECTIONS.....77
10. **Khudaynazarova Salomat Ruzibaevna, Kuryazova Sharofat Masharipovna, Tashenova Gulnora Tolipovna**
STATUS OF VITAMIN D IN CHILDREN AND ITS INFLUENCE ON THE COURSE OF PNEUMONIA.....83

ONCOLOGY

11. **Allazov Iskandar Sallakh ugli Allazov Sallakh Allazovich, , Allazov Feruz Niyazovich, Madalimov Akhror Alievich**
MORPHOLOGICAL AND IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL METHODS IN VERIFICATION OF NON-MUSCLE INVASIVE BLADDER CANCER.....90

12. **Djuraev Mirjalol Dehqanovich, Melikulov Asliddin Khamrakulovich**
DIRECT RESULTS OF COMBINED GASTRECTOMY WITH DISTAL HEMIPANCREATECTOMY WITH SPLENECTOMY FOR LOCALLY ADVANCED GASTRIC CANCER.....97
13. **Minnulin Irkin Rashidovich, Mirzakulov Buned Gaybullaevich, Aslanova Lobar Melikmuradowna, Rahimov Nodir Makhammatkulovich**
MODERN METHODS OF VISUALIZATION AND DIAGNOSTIC CAPABILITIES IN URETERAL CANCER: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF TECHNOLOGICAL APPROACHES.....102
14. **Mustafayev Tojiddin Kurbanovich**
NEPHROBLASTOMA IN CHILDREN: TREATMENT STRUCTURE AND CLINICAL OUTCOME ANALYSIS.....108
15. **Polatova Djamila Shagayratovna, Karimova Nargiza Mansurovna, Kahharov Alisher Jamoliddinovich**
THE ROLE OF MACROPHAGES (CD68+) IN THE IMMUNE MICROENVIRONMENT AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE OUTCOMES OF SOFT TISSUE SARCOMAS TREATMENT.....120
16. **Polatova Djamila Shagayratovna, Karimova Nargiza Mansurovna, Kahharov Alisher Jamoliddinovich**
IMMUNE MICROENVIRONMENT OF SOFT TISSUE SARCOMAS: THE ROLE OF T-LYMPHOCYTES AND MACROPHAGES IN PREDICTING THERAPY EFFICACY....126
17. **Tillyashaikhov Mirzagolib Nigmatovich, Xakkulov Erkin Bekmirzayevich, Alimov Jaloliddin Usmonkhon Ugli**
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PROSTATE SPECIFIC ANTIGEN LEVEL AND PROSTATE VOLUME WITH OVERACTIVE BLADDER IN PATIENTS WITH PROSTATE CANCER.....135
18. **Yusupbekov Abrorjon Akhmadjanovich, Djuraev Murjalol Dekhqonovich, Djumanazarov Temirbek Matchanovich, Rasulov Abdugaffor Elmanovich, Rakhimov Okiljon Abdukhalilovich**
ESOPHAGEAL CANCER: THE ROLE OF PREOPERATIVE CHEMOTHERAPY IN COMBINATION TREATMET.....142

TRAUMATOLOGY

19. **Axtamov A'zam, Axtamov Azim**
RESULTS OF TREATMENT OF LAMBAR DYSPLASIA AND CONGENITAL EXTRACTION IN NURTURAL CHILDREN.....148
20. **Jongirov Sobir Abdukhoshimovich, Kholkhujayev Farrukh Ikramovich, Saleev Bahodur Vakhobovich, Abdusamatov Shahriddin Nuriddin Ogli.**
CHRONIC SHOULDER JOINT INSTABILITY: A HISTORICAL REVIEW AND TRENDS IN SURGICAL TREATMENT.....155
21. **Khamidov Obid Abdurakhmanovich, Baymuratova Aziza Charievna**
ULTRASOUND BASED DETECTION OF INTERNAL KNEE JOINT INJURIES AND FORMULATION OF INDIVIDUALIZED REHABILITATION: AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH IN MEDICINE.....166
22. **Kodirov Ma'ruf Abdumajitovich, Mamatkulov Oybek Xoliqovich, Teshayev Temur Nematovich**
RESULTS OF TREATMENT OF FRACTURES OF THE DISTAL END OF THE FEMUR USING THE NEW DEVICE BY THE METHOD OF RETROGRAD BLOCKING INTRAMEDULAR OSTEOSYNTHESIS.....174

23. **Khodzhanov Iskandar Yunusovich, Gaffarov Farrukh Abdualievich**
ANALYSIS OF MODERN TREATMENT METHODS FOR PATIENTS WITH BOAT FRACTURES AND DISTAL SYNDESMOSIS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....179
24. **Ruziev Shakhzod Olimdjon ugli, Shorustamov Mukhammad Tadjalievich**
MODERN ASPECTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF ULNAR FRACTURES: ANALYSIS OF METHODS, CLINICAL APPROACHES AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS.....187
25. **Temurov Alisher Akmaljon o'g'li**
IMPROVEMENT OF OSTEOSYNTHESIS METHODS FOR DISTAL INTERCOSTAL SYNDESMOSIS RUPTURE.....198
26. **Yamshchikov Oleg Nikolaevich, Yemelyanov Sergey Aleksandrovich, Tilyakov Xasan Azizovich**
RESULTS OF THE APPLICATION OF ADVANCED OSTEOSYNTHESIS IN DIAPHYSEAL FRACTURES OF THE HUMERUS.....204

INTERNAL MEDICINE, ALLERGOLOGY AND IMMUNOLOGY

27. **Allazov Salakh Allazovich**
CLASSIFICATION OF SCIENCES, INCLUDING MEDICAL.....211
28. **Khamraev Abror Asrarovich, Tursunova Minavara Ulugbekovna, Abdullaev Ulugbek Sayfullaevich**
MOLECULAR-GENETIC ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHRONIC PANCREATITIS OF DIFFERENT GENESIS.....217
29. **Saidova Shakhnoza Aripovna, Musayeva Lola Jurayevna, Ilkhamova Zilola Erkindjanovna, Baykhanova Dilrabo Djamaliddinovna**
PATHOGENETIC RATIONALE FOR THE NECESSITY OF REINFUSION OF ASCITIC FLUID IN PATIENTS WITH LIVER CIRRHOSIS.....224
30. **Xoshimov Bobir Luxmonovich, Kuylanov Baxtiyor Bazorboyevich**
EFFECT OF CHRONIC STRESS ON GENERATIONAL HYPOCAMP MORPHOLOGY.....230
31. **Bilalov Bakhodir Erkinovich, Bilalov Erkin Nazimovich, Oripov Okilkhon Ilyasovich.**
RESULTS OF EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES ON THE ANTI-ADHESIVE ACTIVITY OF A HYDROGEL BASED ON THE SODIUM SALT OF CARBOXYMETHYLCELLULOSE.....237
32. **Khudoykulova Farida Vafokulovna**
THE IMPORTANCE OF NUTRITION AND PHYSICAL ACTIVITY IN TREATING NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE.....245

MORPHOLOGY

33. **Berkinov Ulugbek Bazarbayevich, Ermatov Boratjon Raxmatovich**
A MATHEMATICAL MODEL FOR ESTIMATING THE LENGTH OF THE ESOPHAGUS BASED ON ANTHROPOMETRIC INDICATORS, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT GENDER.....256
34. **Indiaminov Sayit Indiaminovich, Jabborov Otabek Yusupovich**
PATHOPHYSIOLOGY AND PATHOMORPHOLOGY OF PULMONARY CONTUSIONS IN CLOSED BLUNT CHEST TRAUMA262
35. **Oripov Firdavs Suratovich, Togayeva Gulnora Siddiqovna**
REACTIVE MORPHOFUNCTIONAL CHANGES IN THE PANCREATIC PARENCHYMA IN EXPERIMENTAL HYPERTHYROIDISM271

36. **Tojiboyev Temur Topvoldi Ogli, Makhamov Nosirjon Juraevich**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE KIDNEYS DURING GESTATIONAL PYELONEPHRITIS IN THE SECOND AND THIRD PREGNANCIES.....278

OPHTHALMOLOGY

37. **Mamasoliev Zokhidjon Nematovich, Rustamjonov Abdurashid Bakhram Ugli, Axmedov Nozimbek Numonbek Ugli**
MODERN EPIDEMIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ACUTE GLAUCOMA ATTACK IN VALLEY CONDITIONS IN ACCORDANCE WITH NON-COMMUNICABLE CHRONIC DISEASE COMORBIDITY.....286
38. **Khakimova Sakhiba Ziyadulloevna, Gaffarova Parvina Abdurafikovna, Azizov Mardon Mavlonovich**
THE ROLE AND CHARACTERISTICS OF DOPAMINE IN THE RETINAL LAYER OF THE EYE IN PATIENTS WITH PARKINSON'S DISEASE.....295

ENDOCRINOLOGY

39. **Kodirova Nargizakhon Umarovna, Djuraeva Aziza Shakhzadeevna**
METABOLIC NATURE OF OBESITY AND PREDIABETES IN THE CONTEXT OF PERIPHERAL NEUROPATHY.....304
40. **Magzumova Shahknoza, Vosikov Botirbek**
NEUROENDOCRINE MECHANISMS OF COMORBIDITY BETWEEN ANXIETY-DEPRESSIVE DISORDERS AND HYPOTHYROIDISM.....315

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

41. **Ibragimova Malika Khudaiberganovna, Ruzikulova Munira Shukhrat Kizi.**
IMPROVING PERIODONTAL CARE IN UZBEKISTAN USING A CONCEPTUAL APPROACH TO IMPROVE ITS QUALITY.....321
42. **Sanakulov Jamshed Olloberdiyevich**
CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PREVENTING PERIODONTAL DISEASES DEVELOPED DUE TO WATER CONSUMPTION FROM UNDERGROUND WELLS.....333

SURGERY

43. **Allazov Salakh Allazovich.**
EPICYSTOSTOMY, CYSTOCUTANEOSTOMY, EPICYSTOCUTANEOSTOMY.....344
44. **Askarov Pulat Azadovich, Akbarov Mirshavkat Mirolimovich**
HYBRID MINIMALLY INVASIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TREATMENT OF COMPLICATED FORMS OF CHOLELITHIASIS.....351
45. **Iskandarov Yusuf Nazimovich**
COMPREHENSIVE SURGICAL APPROACH TO PATIENTS WITH VENTRAL HERNIA AND MORBID OBESITY.....356

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

46. **Davronov Usmon Farmonkulovich, Tadjibayev Dilshod Anorboyevich, Normuradov Nodir Alisherovich, Narzullayev Ilgor Dilmurodovich.**
VASOMOTOR RHINITIS: UNRESOLVED PROBLEMS TO DATE.....365

47. Davronov Usmon Farmonkulovich, Narzullayev Ilgor Dilmurodovich.	
DIAGNOSTIC ASSESSMENT OF THE CALORIC TEST IN VESTIBULAR DISORDERS.....	373
48. Dustboboyev Dilshod, Khayitov Alisher.	
THE TACTICS OF CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT OF EXUDATIVE OTITIS MEDIA IN CHILDREN.....	379
49. Khodjiyeva Kamilla Feruzovna, Rasulova Kibriyo Abdurakhmon Qizi	
THE USE OF VESTIBULAR TESTS IN PATIENTS TO DETERMINE THE LEVEL OF LESION OF THE VESTIBULAR APPARATUS.....	386
50. Narzullayev Ilgor Dilmurodovich, Uktamov Diyorbek Shukhratovich	
DIAGNOSTICAL EVALUATION OF CALORIC NISTAGMA IN VESTIBULAR DISORDERS.....	393
51. Narzullayev Ilgor Dilmurodovich, Uktamov Diyorbek Shukhratovich, Eshpulatov Abdusattor ugli	
CHANGES IN ROTATIONAL TEST DATA IN PATIENTS WITH CERVICAL OSTEOCHONDROSIS.....	499
52. Nasretdinova Makhzuna Takhsinovna, Tadjibayev Dilshod Anorboyevich, Erkinova Kamola	
MODERN CONCEPTS OF VASOMOTOR RHINITIS.....	406
53. Nasretdinova Makhzuna Takhsinovna, Tadjibayev Dilshod Anorboyevich, Normuradov Nodir	
IMPROVING CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT TACTICS IN WOMEN OF CHILDBEARING AGE WITH VASOMOTOR RHINITIS.....	412
54. Normirova Nargiza Nazarovna, , Davronov Usmon Farmonkulovich	
STUDY OF POSITIONAL PAROXYSMAL NYSTAGMUS IN PATIENTS WITH DIZZINESS.....	420
55. Rasulova Kibriyo Abdurakhmon qizi, , Erkinova Kamola Faxriddinovna, Normuradov Nodir Alisherovich	
STUDIES OF POST-ROTATIONAL NYSTAGMUS IN ADOLESCENTS.....	425
56. Rasulova Kibriyo Abdurakhmon qizi, , Erkinova Kamola Faxriddinovna, , Normuradov Nodir Alisherovich	
OPTIMISATION OF DIAGNOSIS OF VARIOUS FORMS OF VESTIBULAR DYSFUNCTION.....	432
57. Shodiyev Anvar Erkinovich, Akramov Shamsiddin Abdisamadovich, Normurodov Nodir	
OPTIMIZATION OF DIAGNOSTICS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC PURULENT OTITIS MEDIA.....	438
58. Tadjibayev Dilshod Anorboyevich, Shodiyev Anvar Erkinovich, Normuradov Nodir Alisherovich	
VASOMOTOR RHINITIS IN THE CLINICAL PRACTICE OF A GENERAL PRACTITIONER.....	444
59. Tadjibayev Dilshod Anorboyevich, Shodiyev Anvar Erkinovich, Normuradov Nodir Alisherovich	
A NEW APPROACH IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC VASOMOTOR RHINITIS.....	451
60. Uktamov Diyorbek Shuxratovich, Narzullayev Ilgor Dilmurodovich	
ASSESSMENT OF THE VESTIBULAR ANALYZER IN IMPAIRED BALANCE FUNCTION.....	457
61. Xatamov Jakhongir Abruyevich	
ON THE ISSUE OF RHINOSEPTOPLASTY FOR DEFORMITIES OF THE EXTERNAL NOSE WITH A DEVIATED NASAL SEPTUM.....	463

UDK 616.284-002.253

DUSTBOBOYEV Dilshod
KHAYITOV Alisher

Samarkand State Medical Institute Samarkand, Uzbekistan

THE TACTICS OF CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT OF EXUDATIVE OTITIS MEDIA IN CHILDREN

For citation: Dustboboyev Dilshod, Khayitov Alisher. The tactics of conservative treatment of exudative otitis media in children. // Journal of Biomedicine and practice. - 2025, vol. 10, issue 4.

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17088018>

INTRODUCTION

This article analyzes the literature on the problem of treatment of exudative otitis media. Exudative otitis media is a polyetiologic inflammatory disease of the middle ear, in the etiopathogenesis of which the dysfunction of the auditory tube plays a key role. The pathomorphologic substrate of exudative otitis media is chronic catarrhal inflammation of the mucous membrane mainly of the meso-, hypotympanum and auditory tube, and clinical signs are the presence of exudate in the tympanic cavity, absence of signs of acute inflammation and defect of the tympanic membrane. The most common cause of exudative otitis media is respiratory viral infections, the second cause is acute otitis media. The prevalence of exudative otitis media depends on age and, according to various authors, is up to 35% in children of the 1st year of life; 3-5 years - 10-30%; 6-7 years - 3-10%; 9-10 years - 1-3%. Exudative otitis media is the most frequent cause of hearing loss in children aged 2 to 7 years - during mass examinations of children it is found in 30.2% of cases. Studies by foreign authors confirm the independent resolution of most cases of exudative otitis media, otherwise patients need treatment. Modern medicine considers many treatment options for exudative otitis media, up to the alternative of using hearing aids for patients with contraindications to other types of treatment. In a number of countries, in the diagnosis of exudative average otitis media, it often prescribes medicines or surgical treatment of patients without active observation.

Key words: exudative otitis media, treatment tactics, tympanotomy.

ДУСТБОБОЕВ Дилшод
ХАЙИТОВ Алишер

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

ТАКТИКА КОНСЕРВАТИВНОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ЭКССУДАТИВНОГО СРЕДНЕГО ОТИТА У ДЕТЕЙ

РЕЗЮМЕ

В этой статье анализируется литература о проблеме лечения экссудативного среднего отита. Среда экссудативного отита представляет собой полиэтиологическое воспалительное заболевание среднего уха, в этиопатогенезе, из которого играет дисфункция слуховой трубки. Патоморфологический субстрат экссудативного среднего отита-это хроническое воспаление слизистой оболочки, в основном мезо-, гипотимпанума и слуховой трубки, а клинические признаки являются присутствием экссудата в барабанной полости, отсутствие признаков острая воспаления и дефекта барабанной перепонки. Наиболее распространенной причиной экссудативного среднего отита является респираторное вирусное инфекции, второй причиной является острый средний отит. Распространенность экссудативного среднего отита зависит от возраста и, по мнению различных авторов, составляет до 35% у детей 1 -го года жизни; 3-5 лет-10-30%; 6-7 лет-3-10%; 9-10 лет-1-3%. Среда экссудативного отита является наиболее частой причиной потери слуха у детей в возрасте от 2 до 7 лет - во время массовых исследований детей она обнаруживается в 30,2% случаев. Исследования, проведенные иностранными авторами, подтверждают независимое разрешение большинства случаев экссудативного среднего отита, в противном случае пациенты нуждаются в лечении. Современная медицина рассматривает многие варианты лечения для экссудативного среднего отита, в зависимости от альтернативы использования слуховых аппаратов для пациентов с противопоказаниями для других типов лечения. В ряде стран, при диагностике экссудативного среднего отита, часто назначает лекарства или хирургическое лечение пациентам без активного наблюдения.

Ключевые слова: экссудативная среда отит, тактика лечения, тимпаностомия

**DUSTBOBOYEV Dilshod
XAYITOV Alisher**

**BOLALARDA EKSDATIV O'RTA O'TKIR OTITNI KONSERVATIV DAVOLASH
TAKTIKASI****REZYUME**

Ushbu moddaga kiritilgan joriy moddaning ekstrativativ Otitning o'rtacha medialarini davolash muammosi bo'yicha adabiyotlarni tahlil qiladi. Ekozativ otitning muhiti - bu o'rta quloqning poliopatogenezining poliopatogenezining poliopatogenezining poliopatogenezining poliopatogenezining polieopatogenezining poliopatogenezini kasallikidir. Ekozativ o'rtacha otitning patomorforfologik substrati shilliq qavatning surunkali yallig'lanishi, asosan metom, gipotmeum va eshitish naychasi, o'tkir yallig'lanish va nuqsonning yo'qligi. Timshanik membrana. Exudasiya o'rtacha otitining eng keng tarqalgan sababi - nafas olish virusli infektsiyasi, ikkinchi sabab o'rtacha otitning o'rtacha muhitidir. Eksudasiya o'rtacha otitining tarqalishi yoshga bog'liq va turli mualliflarning so'zlariga ko'ra, hayotning 1-yilidagi bolalarda 35 foizgacha; 3-5 yil - 10-30%; 6-7 yil - 3-10%; 9-10 yil-1-3%. Ekozatsion otitning muhiti 2 yoshdan 7 yoshgacha bo'lgan bolalarda - bolalarning ommaviy tadqiqotlar davomida, 30,2% hollarda uchraydi. Xorijiy mualliflar tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlar ekssudativ otitning aksariyat holatlarining mustaqil hal etilishini tasdiqlaydi, aks holda bemorlarga davolanish kerak. Zamonaviy tibbiyot ekspeditsiyalar uchun kontrendikatsiyalar uchun kontrendikatsiyaga ega bo'lgan bemorlar uchun yordam berish vositalaridan foydalanish alternativasi qarang, ekstrumativ o'rtacha vositalarning ko'plab davolash imkoniyatlarini ko'rib chiqadi. Bir qator mamlakatlarda ekssudativ o'rtacha otitning tashxisida u ko'pincha faol kuzatilmasdan kasallarni yoki bemorlarni dori-darmonlarni yoki jarrohlik davolashda buyuradi.

Kalit so'zlar: ekssuzativ muhit, davolash taktikasi, timpanostomiya.

The World Health Organization predicts that by 2030 the number of people with socially significant hearing defects will increase by more than 30% [6]. At least 30% of all cases of hearing loss are caused by middle ear pathology. In recent decades, many authors have noted an increase in the incidence of exudative otitis media (ESO), with it accounting for 15-17% of all ear diseases [7]. Epidemiologic studies show that ESO affects 50-80% of children under 5 years of age [8,9], two out of 1000 children have serious complications. As a result, they endure radical middle ear surgeries that reduce the quality of life of the child, who subsequently needs social adaptation [10,11]. This confirms the seriousness of the problem of ESO and brings this pathology to the forefront both in the country and in the world as a whole [7,12].

In the scientific medical literature, exudative otitis media has a number of other names. Often the name depends on the physician-researcher's view of the causal role of one or another factor in the stages of disease development. A number of physicians emphasize the main role of auditory tube obstruction in the development of the disease and use such terms as “pharyngotubotympanal disease”, “chronic tubal obstruction”, “tubotympanal catarrh”, “tubotympanitis”, “otosalpingitis” (2,3.). At the same time, other otorhinolaryngologists adhere to the point of view of the root cause of this disease in the role of vacuum in the formation of liquid sterile content in the middle ear, sweating through the capillary wall, which gave rise to another kind of names “middle ear hydrocele”, “hydrotympanum”, “serotympanum”, “serous otitis media”, “simple serous otitis media”, “sterile middle otitis media”, etc. (4,5). In turn, other names of this pathology are associated with the discharge of inflammatory exudate into the tympanic cavity, so the disease is called exudative otitis media, exudative catarrhal otitis media, otitis media with exudate, etc. (8).

The terms “secretory catarrh of the middle ear” and “secretory otitis media” have been proposed to emphasize the increased secretory activity of the mucous glands of the middle ear mucosa, and to designate forms of this pathology with sticky, viscous contents - “glue ear” (glueear), “mucoid ear”, “seromucoid catarrh of the middle ear”, viscous contents - “glue ear” (glueear), “mucoid ear”, “seromucoid catarrh of the middle ear” (5,6) Hemorrhagic forms of otitis media are designated as idiopathic hematotympanum, or hemorrhagic serous otitis media (6.). Diagnoses that define a mild, superficial form of middle ear mucosal disease are used: “acute nonpurulent middle otitis media,” “catarrhal otitis media,” “catarrh of the auditory tube and middle ear,” “simple middle otitis media,” “difficult catarrh,” etc. (7).

In Western scientific and medical literature, the term “serous otitis media” is most often used, which characterizes a mild, initial form of the disease and is based on serous inflammation of the middle ear mucosa. In the literature of European countries, the name “secretory otitis media” is used, meaning superficial inflammation of the middle ear mucosa with hypersecretion of glands and increased secretory activity of bocaloid cells, which corresponds to forms with viscous contents in the tympanic cavity prevalent in children. In the CIS, including the Republic of Uzbekistan, the term “exudative otitis media” is most commonly used, emphasizing the importance of complex and deep inflammatory processes in the middle ear.

Differences in the designation of the same disease indicate that the process of the appearance of liquid, non-purulent contents in the tympanic cavity is not clear at all. In addition, there are clinical variants of the disease, in connection with which difficulties in diagnosis and treatment are not excluded. Conservative and surgical methods are used in the treatment of ESO. Surgical treatment of ESO is recommended in the majority of cases when conservative therapy is ineffective and when the duration of the disease is 2-4 weeks or more [13,14]. Conservative methods of treatment include: active surveillance; oral or topical administration of steroidal drugs, antibiotics, antihistamines, decongestants; and blowing of the auditory tubes. Surgical treatment methods include: paracentesis, tympanic cavity bypass (insertion of a ventilation tube) with/without simultaneous adenoidectomy in children, laser myringotomy, middle ear surgery.

Active observation (Activeobservation) is the process of regular check-ups of the patient, including evaluation of hearing and lingual development. It is a method in which no treatment is prescribed, but the patient is constantly monitored by the attending physician. Although the patient receives regular consultations with the doctor, the choice and responsibility for treatment decisions remains with the patient or parents (if the patient is a minor). Another term previously used was dynamic monitoring or watchfulwaiting [5].

Ear tube blowing is a technique in which the Eustachian tube (the tube that connects the middle ear and the nasopharynx) is opened by increasing pressure in the nasal cavity. The technique of this method is to conduct pressurized air into the middle ear through the eustachian tube to equalize the pressure and evacuate secretion from the tympanic cavity [15]. This can be achieved by forced exhalation with closed mouth and nose, Politzer blowing of the auditory tubes, and catheterization of the auditory tubes. In the United States and in Europe, Autoinflation for the treatment of exudative otitis media, which is performed with a balloon with a nozzle, is a common method often used for the treatment of exudative otitis media in children [16].

Antibiotics, antihistamines, decongestants are prescribed by physicians in different countries on a case-by-case basis. Steroid drugs (systemic or topical) are used in order to evacuate the secretion as soon as possible and thus restore the normal functioning of the air conduction circuit [13]. Myringotomy (paracentesis, tympanotomy) is a surgical intervention in which an incision is made in the tympanic membrane for therapeutic and diagnostic purposes. The incision is made with a special needle (with a lance-shaped blade) on the posterior-lower part of the tympanic membrane, a few millimeters long. In this way it is possible to inject medication into the middle ear. Some clinics perform laser myringotomy[5].

Tympanostomy (tympanostomy, installation of ventilation tubes) is a surgical option for the treatment of exudative otitis media and is usually used in case of repeated filling of the tympanic cavity with exudate in the absence of effect after repeated tympanotomy. It consists of inserting ventilation tubes into the tympanic membrane to restore pressure and improve the exudate outflow and allows for the trans-stympanic administration of various drugs. The criteria for this intervention vary depending on the treatment protocols of the country.

In children with exudative otitis media, many countries include nasopharyngeal endoscopy to determine the degree of lymphoid hypertrophy (adenoids) in the examination protocol. If there is a blockage of lymphoid tissue at the mouth of the auditory tubes, adenoidectomy is indicated. In some cases, this operation is sufficient to restore full hearing and normal functioning of the structures of the tympanic cavity. In some cases, more often in adults, more radical surgical interventions are performed on the middle ear to sanitize the tympanic cavity [12].

Despite the wide discussion in the literature on the etiology, diagnosis, and treatment of exudative otitis exudata, there are different views on the choice of treatment tactics [19].

In the UK, the National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence (NICE) has developed guidelines for the diagnosis and treatment of exudative otitis media. The guidelines include specialist consultation, active surveillance, surgical and non-surgical intervention. According to these guidelines, patients are first consulted by a general practitioner (GP) and referred to an otorhinolaryngologist for evaluation if hearing loss is suspected, especially in children with delayed speech development. This is followed by a 3-month follow-up with the specialist. If the condition worsens and the hearing loss increases, the choice between surgical or non-surgical treatment is made depending on the patient's medical history. With non-surgical treatment, the doctor should provide information about the benefits and risks of treatment to the patient, then offer hearing aids as an alternative when surgery is contraindicated or unacceptable. Typically, a tympanotomy is performed followed by placement of ventilation tubes (shunts). In the absence of persistent and/or frequent symptoms of upper respiratory tract infections in adults, a one-stage adenoidectomy is performed. Ventilatory tubes are subsequently removed spontaneously within 6 months to 1 year, or they are

removed by an otorhinolaryngologist within the same time frame. The result is monitored by repeated audiometry and tympanometry after removal of the ventilation tubes after 2 weeks and 1 month. (NICE).

Based on a number of systematic reviews in the field, it can be concluded that in the United States of America otolaryngologists are more likely to use the Watchfulwaiting strategy. That is, the patient is seen by an ENT physician for 3 months, followed by a conclusion that in the United States, otorhinolaryngologists are more likely to use a strategy of active surveillance (Watchfulwaiting). That is, within 3 months, the patient is observed by an ENT doctor with a follow-up audiogram. In the absence of positive dynamics after 3 months, patients are offered surgical treatment in the form of tympanotomy with subsequent installation of ventilation tubes (shunts). Obviously, the treatment algorithm in the USA is similar to the treatment algorithm in the United Kingdom. In America there are both traditional methods of treatment and non-traditional methods (homeopathy, manual therapy, dietary supplements), the latter of which are not welcomed [13,15]. Types of treatment for exudative otitis media are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 - Types and tactics of treatment for exudative otitis media used in the USA. Evidence-based Practice Center Systematic Review Protocol: Otitis Media with Effusion: Comparative Effectiveness of Treatments, July 30, 2012

Surgical intervention
Myringotomy
Installation of a tympanostomy (ventilation) tube
Adenoidectomy with or without myringotomy
revenge
Medical treatment
Antibiotics and antimicrobials
Nasal Steroids
Systemic Steroids
Other types of treatment
Purgeingstachievyh pipes
Additional and alternative treatment
Hearing aids
Other types of treatment

In Germany, the surgical method, tympanotomy with/without a ventilation tube, is recognized as an effective treatment. In addition to tympanotomy, simultaneous adenoidectomy is performed in children in Germany. The benefits of surgery should always outweigh the potential risks [14]. In France, Turkey, Malaysia and other developed countries, the method of active follow-up is used in patients with exudative otitis media detected for the first time, followed by surgical intervention in the absence of positive dynamics after 3 months.

We present the treatment tactics used during the initial examination by a general practitioner (pediatrician) for suspected exudative otitis media in Malaysia. According to the reflected scheme, the initial examination includes a therapeutic examination and active surveillance tactics. Upon confirmation of the diagnosis of ESO, the patient is referred for consultation to an otorhinolaryngologist, which is specialized medical care.

We also describe the tactics of managing a patient with exudative otitis media by an otorhinolaryngologist, i.e. the algorithm of actions for non-surgical and surgical types of treatment of patients diagnosed with exudative otitis media. This tactic of introducing patients with ESO has been approved by the Malaysian Ministry of health.

As conservative treatment methods in all of the above-mentioned countries, antibiotics, steroids, antihistamines, decongestants are used, individually and in combinations (for example, antibiotics + decongestants, antihistamines + steroids).

There are also randomized controlled trials indicating the absence of significant positive dynamics during ESO when using only conservative treatment methods.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, as in other CIS countries, treatment primarily begins with drug therapy in the combined and combined use of decongestants, antibiotics and antihistamines. In the absence of a positive effect, surgical intervention is performed in the form of a tympanotomy with or without the installation of a ventilation tube, depending on the quality of the exudate, with simultaneous adenoidectomy in children with blockage of the mouth of the auditory tubes. Transtympanic administration of steroid drugs to patients after tympanotomy and/or without a ventilation tube is considered effective, which contributes to the early restoration of middle ear function.

This analysis does not include patients with exudative otitis media with concomitant hereditary diseases such as Down syndrome and congenital cleft palate (cleft lip, cleft palate). Thus, based on the analysis of the literature, it can be noted that some of the commonly used treatment methods are: active monitoring, self-filling method, antibiotics, antihistamines, decongestants, steroid medications (systemic or topical), myringotomy (paracentesis, tympanotomy), bypass surgery of the tympanic cavity.

Treatment tactics are constantly changing and improving, striving for more progressive methods. The choice of treatment tactics for exudative otitis media depends on the diagnostic and treatment protocol followed by the country. Summarizing the above, it is worth paying attention to the fact that otorhinolaryngologists from different countries do not have a single point of view when choosing a treatment method for this disease.

REFERENCES | ЧОҚҚИ | ИҚТИБОСЛР:

1. Amonov Sh., Saidov S., Bahranov M. EXUDATIVE OTITIS MEDIA - QUESTIONS OF ETIOPATHOGENESIS AND THERAPY // Journal of Dentistry and Craniofacial Research. - 2021. - V. 2. - No. 2. - P. 45-48. (in Russ)
2. Berkman ND, Wallace IF, Steiner MJ, et al. Otitis media with effusion: comparative effectiveness of treatments // Comparative Effectiveness. - 2013. - №101. – P. 10-14.
3. Hesham A, Hussien A, Hussein A. Topical mitomycin C application before myringotomy and ventilation tube insertion: does it affect the final outcome? // Ear Nose Throat J. – 2012. - 91(8). – P. 45-49.
4. Perera R, Glasziou PP, Heneghan CJ, McLellan J, Williamson I Autoinflation for hearing loss associated with otitis media with effusion. – 2013. – 219 p.
5. Simpson SA, Lewis R, van der Voort J, Butler CC. Oral or topical nasal steroids for hearing loss associated with otitis media with effusion in children. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews 2011, Issue 5: <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/14651858.CD001935.pub3/abstract>
6. Grommets (ventilation tubes) for hearing loss associated with otitis media with effusion in children/6 October 2010/Authors: Browning GG, Rovers MM, Williamson I, Lous J, Burton MJ. : <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/20927726>
7. Sedlmayer B. et al. Factors influencing the postoperative course and occurrence of relapse of exudative otitis media in children // Russian Otolaryngology. - 2009. - No. 5. - P. 54-59.(in Russ)

8. Browning GG, Rovers MM, Williamson I, et al; Grommets (ventilation tubes) for hearing loss associated with otitis media with effusion in children // *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* – 2010. - 6(10). – P. 45-52.
9. Van Zon A, van der Heijden GJ, van Dongen TM, et al; Antibiotics for otitis media with effusion in children // *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* – 2012. - №9. – P. 74-79.
10. Ina F. Wallace, Nancy D. Berkman, Kathleen N. Lohr, Melody F. Harrison, Adam J. Kimple, Michael J. Steiner Surgical Treatments for Otitis Media with Effusion // *A Systematic.* – 2014. - №2. – P. 21-26.
11. SILKE BURKERT, CH. RASINSKI, R. BURKERT, K. NEUMANN Otitis media with effusion – current management in children. – 2012. – 216 p.
12. Griffin G, Flynn CA Antihistaminiques avec ou sans décongestionnants pour l'otitemoyenne avec effusion (OME) (otiteséreuse) chez l'enfant - / 7 septembre 2011: <http://www.cochrane.org/fr/CD003423/antihistaminiques-avec-ou-sans-decongestionnants-pour-lotite-moyenne-avec-effusion-ome-otite-sereuse-chez-lenfant>
13. Magomedov M. M. et al. Exudative otitis media. Modern concepts and relevance of the problem // *Bulletin of Otorhinolaryngology.* - 2012. - No. 5. - P. 93-97. (in Russ)
14. Khaitov A. A. et al. Optimization of one-stage sanitation of the nasopharynx and tympanic cavity in case of recurrent exudative otitis media // *Current scientific research in the modern world.* - 2018. - No. 1-8. - P. 81-84. (in Russ)
15. Umrillaevich L. G. et al. OTITIS MEDIA WITH EFFUSION IN CHILDREN: A REVIEW // *JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE.* – 2024. – Т. 9. – №. 1. (in Russ)
16. Usmonov S. H., Narbayev Z. K. IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MODERN ENDOSCOPIC METHODS IN THE TREATMENT OF ACUTE TUBOOTITIS // *Экономика и социум.* – 2022. – №. 10-2 (101). – С. 194-197. (in Russ)
17. Imatov O. S., Rizaev J. A., Toxtayev G. S. A SURVEY OF BULLOUS DISEASES CLINICOEPIDEMIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS // *Central Asian Journal of Medicine.* – 2025. – №. 2. – С. 65-70.
18. Alimdjanovich R. J., Ugli T. N. K. CLINICAL AND ANATOMICAL FEATURES OF NASAL DEFORMITY IN PATIENTS WITH UNILATERAL CLEFT LIP AND PALATE AFTER CHEILOPLASTY // *The American Journal of Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research.* – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 08. – С. 13-22.
19. Фаттаева Д., Ризаев Ж., Рахимова Д. ОСОБЕННОСТИ КЛИНИЧЕСКОГО ТЕЧЕНИЯ ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО ГАЙМОРИТА ПРИ БРОНХО-ЛЕГОЧНОЙ ПАТОЛОГИИ // *SCIENTIFIC IDEAS OF YOUNG SCIENTISTS.* – 2021. – С. 28.
20. Polatova Djamila , Madaminov Ahmad, Raximov Nodir . Significance of expression PD-L1 and p53 proteins in human papillomavirus-associated oropharyngeal squamous cell carcinoma // *Journal of Biomedicine and Practice.* 2022, vol . 7, issue 4, pp . 144-151
21. Abdurakhmonov F. R., Rakhimov N. M., Abdurakhmonova F. F. Special choices for the treatment of complications of the soft tissue injuries of the facial region // *The American Journal of Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research.* – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 10. – С. 24-26.

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000